

Effect of hafen 20EC on brain cholesterol, glycogen and total lipid in albino rat

Prabhu N. Saxena and Dinesh C. Sharma
Department of Zoology, School of Life Sciences,
Institute of Basic Science, Dr. B.R. Ambedkar University
Agra - 282 002 (U.P.), India

Abstract

Albino rats treated with acute (381 mg/kg body wt.) and subchronic (20 mg/kg body wt.) doses of hafen 20EC revealed insignificant increase in tissue cholesterol and glycogen level but a significant increase ($P < 0.02$) in lipid level. The possible pathway/process has been discussed.

Key words : albino rat, cholesterol, glycogen, total lipid, hafen 20 EC

Introduction

Hafen 20EC (AI: Fenvelrate) is a type II pyrethroid containing α cyno group. This pesticide has already been reported to enhance neurotoxicity in mammals. In the present investigation albino rats were used as experimental animals and the brain, the site of action of pyrethroid (Husain *et al.* 1991) has been selected as target organ as it coordinates all the physiological activities.

Materials and Methods

Captivated and acclimated twenty albino rats (*Rattus norvegicus*) used in the present investigation were selected from inbred colony. Rats were maintained in polypropylene cages and fed standard feed obtained from M/s. Hindustan Liver Ltd. and water *ab libitum*. The albino rats were divided into five groups, each having four individuals. The test compound used was hafen 20 EC (AI: fenvelrate) (purity is 20 w/w and inert ingredients is 80% w/w).

Standard solution was prepared by dissolving hafen 20EC in groundnut oil. Different doses (1200, 1600, 2000 and 2800 mg/kg body wt.) were administered orally to determine LD_{50} . The mortality pattern was recorded for each dose after 96 hours. The data were analysed statistically by log dose/probit regression method (Finney 1971). Glycogen, cholesterol and total lipid were estimated in brain tissue by the methods of Montgomery (1957), Zak *et al.* (1954), Folch *et al.* (1957), respectively.

Results and Discussion

The calculated LD_{50} of hafen 20EC after 96 hour treatment was found to be 1991 mg/kg body weight. In the present

study cholesterol level in brain tissue did not register any significant increase in comparison to control counterpart both in acute and subchronic treatment groups.

However, a significant increase ($P < 0.02$) was observed in the concentration of total lipid in acute and subchronic treatment. Springfield *et al.* (1973) also observed an increase in lipid content after pyrethrum intoxication in rats. The increase in brain lipid might be due to an outcome of inactivity of lipase and is in accordance with the observations of Ham and Rose (1969). Kartha and Krishnamurthy (1978) reported that the brain shows a high degree of peroxidation and might be due to the presence of large amount of lipid in brain. Probably the peroxidation of endogenous lipid are inhibited by hafen 20EC which in turn brings out an increase in the lipid level of brain tissue. Maiti *et al.* (1995) observed decreased thyroxin concentration in female mouse on fenvelrate administration as a result of which blood phospholipid gets elevated. Probably similar mechanism might hold true for brain lipid elevation. In stress condition glucose utilization increases (Cremer *et al.* 1980). Some of the glucose is used anaerobically and results in the glycerol formation which in turn is utilized for lipid biosynthesis in brain tissue. Probably similar mechanism might be expected in present investigation.

An insignificant decrease in glycogen ($P > 0.05$) content in brain of hafen 20EC treated rats supported the finding of Sharma (1997). Cremer *et al.* (1980) reported increased rate of glucose utilization following decamethrin administration. To overcome this increasing requirement of glucose, it is quite probable that the stored glycogen of brain undergo glycogenolysis. Husain *et al.* (1991) reported that administration of hafan 20EC causes

depletion of noradrenalin and it could be responsible for glucogenolysis, in turn resulting into glycogen depletion in brain tissue. Some of these parameters might be persuaded to develop early diagnostic marker in hafen 20 EC intoxication.

Table 1. Biochemical changes in the brain of albino rat after hafen 20 EC intoxication.

Biochemical parameters	Hafen 20EC Treatment			
	Day 1 Mean+S.E.	Day 7 Mean+S.E.	Day 14 Mean+S.E.	Day 21 Mean+S.E.
Total lipid (mg/g tissue)	20.50±0.32* 24.38±1.00♦ P<0.02	20.29±0.22* 24.18±1.38♦ P<0.02	20.10±0.97* 25.42±1.30♦ P<0.02	20.19±0.44* 23.62±1.11♦ P<0.02
Cholesterol (mg/g tissue)	25.33±3.27* 29.00±7.05♦ P>0.05	21.00±4.80* 23.20±1.23♦ P>0.05	21.67±5.86* 24.00±4.00♦ P>0.05	22.00±1.33* 24.00±5.92♦ P>0.05
Glycogen (mg/g tissue)	12.67±4.14* 10.80±1.98♦ P>0.05	20.77±0.82* 18.93±1.77♦ P>0.05	15.60±0.25* 14.67±4.88♦ P>0.05	16.67±1.63* 13.40±1.56♦ P>0.05

* Control Set., ♦ Treated Set.

References

Cremer, J.E., V.J. Cunningham, D.E. Ray and G.S. Sarna. 1980. Regional changes in brain glucose utilization in rats given a

pyrethroid insecticide. *Brain Research*, 194: 278-282.

Finney, D.J. 1971. Probit analysis. Cambridge university press pp. 303.

Folch, J., M. Less and G.H.S. Stanley. 1957. A simple method for the isolation and purification of total lipids from animal tissues. *J. Biol. Chem.*, 226: 497.

Han, J.M. and R. Rose. 1969. Platelet adhesiveness and lipoprotein lipase activity in controls and in subjects taking oral contraceptives. *Amer J. Obst. Gynaecol.*, 105: 628-631.

Husain, R., A. Gupta, V.K. Khanna and P.N. Seth. 1991. Neurotoxicological effects of pyrethroid formulation fenvalerate in rats. *Res. Communication in Chemical Patho. and Pharmacol.*, 73(1): 111-114.

Kartha, V.N. and S. Krishnamurthy. 1978. Factors affecting *in vitro* lipid peroxidation of rat brain homo-genate. *Ind. J. Physiol. Pharmacol.*, 22: 44-52.

Maiti, P.K., A. Kar, P. Gupta and S.S. Chaurasia. 1995. Loss of membrane integrity and inhibition of type-I iodothyronine 5' monodeiodinase activity by fenvalerate in female mouse. *Biochem. Biophys. Res. Commun.*, 214(3): 905-909.

Montgomery, R. 1957. Determination of glycogen. *Arch. Biochem. Biophys.*, 67: 378-386.

Springfield, A.C., G.P. Carlson and J.J. Defec. 1973. Liver enlargement and modification of hepatic microsomal drug metabolism in rats by pyrethrum. *Toxicology and Applied Pharmacology*, 24: 298-308.

Zak, B., R.C. Dickenman, E.G. White, H. Burnett and P.J. Cherney. 1954. Rapid estimation of free and total cholesterol. *Amer. J. Clin. Path.*, 24: 1307.